

**INVESTIGATION OF THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF
CARBONATE MINERALS OF THE SOUTHERN ARAL DEPOSITS OF
KARAKALPAKSTAN**

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In this work, the physicochemical properties of natural carbonate minerals from various deposits of Karakalpakstan (Muynak and Kungrad) and methods for obtaining new composite materials and mineral binders were studied. For this, a physicochemical analysis of the compositions of carbonate minerals of the Muynaks and Kungrad deposits of Karakalpakstan was carried out. In this work, the physicochemical properties of natural carbonate minerals from various deposits of Karakalpakstan (Muynak and Kungrad) and methods for obtaining new composite materials and mineral binders were studied. For this, a physicochemical analysis of the compositions of carbonate minerals of the Muynaks and Kungrad deposits of Karakalpakstan was carried out.

The chemical and physico-chemical characteristics of carbonate-clay rocks of the Republic of Karakalpakstan indicate the possibility of their use for the production of various binders of building materials: air lime, building lime, lime-belite binder, hydraulic lime and romancement, as the basis of binders for various purposes [1, 2]. Carbonate rocks consist mainly of calcareous and marl minerals. For the study, several samples were taken from two deposits, differing in the content of marl and carbonate-argillaceous parts. Six average samples were prepared from these samples and subjected to a detailed study. It turned out that the studied objects differ in the content of calcium and magnesium carbonates, silica and alumina compounds. Carbonate rocks consist mainly of calcareous and marl minerals. For the study, several samples were taken from two deposits, differing in the content of marl and carbonate-argillaceous parts. Six average samples were prepared from these samples and subjected to a detailed study. It turned out that the studied objects differ in the content of calcium and magnesium carbonates, silica and alumina compounds.

An analysis of the chemical compositions and physicochemical properties of carbonate minerals makes it possible to choose a rational method for obtaining finished materials from them. This paper presents the results of physical and chemical studies of some marly minerals of Karakalpakstan in order to create important effective binder building materials on their basis.

Therefore, this paper presents the results of experimental data on the study of various binders based on carbonate rocks - marl of the Muynak and Kungrad deposits of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in order to create lime-belite binders. Laboratory chemical studies of natural carbonate minerals were carried out according to GOST 5382-91 [3]. The results of chemical analysis are shown in table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of marl samples

Place of birth of marl	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	l.d.c	Σ
Muynak	7,85	2,05	0,74	47,38	1,13	0,33	1,43	0,53	38,65	100,09
Muynak	7,50	2,07	0,84	47,27	1,17	0,20	0,94	0,49	39,53	100,01
Muynak	7,42	2,03	0,79	47,55	1,10	0,25	0,92	0,50	39,48	100,04
Khodjakul	9,60	3,47	1,11	44,75	0,76	0,13	0,80	0,76	38,70	100,08
Khodjakul	9,76	3,44	0,86	45,64	0,81	Сл.	0,85	0,72	37,81	99,89
Khodjakul	9,71	3,41	1,19	45,20	0,81	Сл.	0,87	0,68	38,06	99,93

As can be seen from the chemical analysis data, the samples used in the work belong to lime marl. The physicochemical composition of marls is a mixture of calcium and magnesium carbonates, silica compounds, alumina and iron hydroxide in the composition of montmorillonite, a certain amount of calcium sulfate in the form of gypsum, a small amount of soluble salts of sulfuric and hydrochloric acids.

The issue of using carbonate-argillaceous rocks of Muynak for the needs of the industry of building materials and construction has not yet been practically resolved. Exploration work, which revealed the nature of the occurrence, structures and chemical composition of the rocks, determined the possibility of using Muynak carbonate-argillaceous deposits for the production of binders. Significant diversity was noted in the chemical and mineralogical composition along the strike and the thickness of the occurrence of rocks of various deposits. Thus, the presented research shows that the physicochemical properties of marl minerals of the deposits: Muynak and Khodzhakul indicate the possibility of their use as a basis for obtaining binders.

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